

Types of Exercises for Developing Students' Written Speech

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 01 Dec 2025; **Accepted:** 02 Jan 2025; **Published:** 07 Feb 2025

Abstract: This article considers the types of exercises for developing students' written speech. The main areas of work on developing students' speech are analyzed in it. Writing serves as a means of communication between people when direct communication is impossible, when they are separated by space and time. Written speech develops on the basis of oral speech.

Keys words: types of exercises, students' written speech, means of communication, when direct communication, complex constructions, communicative methods.

The importance of learning a foreign language is undeniable. However, there are many problems during training. These include the problem of increasing the effectiveness of teaching oral speech in foreign language lessons, which is directly related to the gap between theory and practice and the passive nature of educational activities, while an educated active person capable of continuous self-education, self-development and self-improvement becomes the absolute value of society. If modern pedagogical technologies are used in the process of teaching foreign language oral speech, this will increase the effectiveness of teaching this type of speech activity. During the study of grammar, one of the main goals is to develop students' ability to use grammatical structures in speech. The use of mini-dialogues containing personally oriented questions is one of the effective ways to achieve this. Human speech is a kind of mirror of culture and education. By speech, one can immediately determine the level of thinking of the speaker, as well as the level of his development. Only through the development of speech is it possible to form and improve thinking, imagination, emotions. Written speech is the result of expressing thoughts using the writing system of a certain language. The main function of written speech is to record oral speech, with the goal of preserving it in space and time. It is the most difficult for students because:

- 1) it is always more complex and complete than oral, sentences are larger, complex constructions are used more often, more bookish words;
- 2) such important components as pauses, gestures, logical stress, intonations are not used;
- 3) written speech is complicated by spelling. "Teaching should be organized in such a way that reading and writing are needed for something by the student; writing should be meaningful for the student, should be caused by a natural need, necessity, included in a task that is vital for the student. It is possible to develop the written speech of schoolchildren in English lessons using three methods: imitative, communicative and the method of construction.

Imitative methods can also be called "by model" methods. Imitation methods include analysis of model texts, synthesis of one's own language constructions, search activity, choice of words and other language tools, modeling of model texts and construction of sentences and texts based on these models, generalization, derivation of rules and even creativity - retellings and written summaries with creative additions or changes, staging, dramatization, artistic reading and storytelling, imitative and one's own

literary creativity. Methods of teaching speech "by model" have their own extensive set of techniques, types of student work: these are numerous types of retelling of read texts, written summaries of various types: with linguistic analysis of the text, with illustrations, with a change in genre. The arsenal of "by model" methods also includes smaller, private exercises: composing sentences or components of a text based on a given type or on a model, which may also have been compiled by students; practicing pronunciation, intonation, pauses, stresses based on the teacher's example of performance, and especially - on understanding the author's - writer's intention or on the basis of artistic performance, various stories and written compositions by analogy with what has been read, and in literary and creative circles - translations, imitations, parodies. "By examples" schoolchildren work on types of speech and on various genres: on description, narration, reasoning; on stylistic, compositional, content features of a story, essay, newspaper article, review of a book read or a play, characteristics, as well as on composing so-called "business papers" - announcements, applications, business letters, telegrams, diary entries. The imitative method is very developed in elementary school, but it cannot be sufficient: teaching "by examples" only prepares students for other methods of speech development.

Communicative methods are based on the theory of speech activity, in particular on the analysis of the speech act: the method takes into account all its stages - both situational and motivational, and the perception of the interlocutor, and feedback. Communicative methods have their own set of techniques, teaching tools, types of exercise assignments: creating speech situations or choosing them from the flow of life; role-playing games, work, hikes and excursions, paintings, specially organized observations, other ways of accumulating material, impressions; any types of activity that can cause the need for statements; drawing pictures, keeping records and diaries; creating plots from imagination, including fairy tales; choosing a variety of genres - reports, radio appearances, television programs, advertising. This method presupposes a system of students' skills, realized in the process of various kinds of written and oral speech exercises. The construction method is a synthetic method. It is associated with the first two. In the system of teaching "by models" the types of text are analyzed and modeled, and subsequently the construction of one's own texts is carried out according to these models. Construction is also connected with the communicative method, since it provides motivation for speech, its effectiveness, determines the social and personal functions of speech. The method of text construction has a large set of techniques and types of speech exercises; most of them usually perform a preparatory or auxiliary function: they are woven into the process of preparing a speech exercise at its different stages. This is vocabulary work, work on a phrase, work on a sentence, logical: work with concepts and constructing their definitions, comparing objects, natural phenomena according to their features, exercises based on text theory: modeling the structure of sample texts and subordinating one's own text to this model, editing one's own text; practicing types of connections in the text; composing texts of various functional and semantic types: description, narration and reasoning, as well as different genres: a story, a landscape sketch, a description of a painting, an essay, a newspaper article, a letter, a riddle, a play; conveying the plot in dialogic form. Developing students' coherent written speech means instilling in them a number of specific skills:

1. comprehend the topic;
2. collect material;
3. arrange the material;
4. use language tools;
5. correct, improve, enhance what has been written.

Small-form written exercises and oral exercises for speech development should be conducted regularly. Successful learning will be achieved only when each exercise is a necessary link in the chain of exercises and is performed systematically. Performing exercises, especially creative ones, should become a habit for students.

Work on developing students' written speech is varied and depends on: a) the age characteristics of students, b) the level of their literary and speech development, c) the type and genre of fiction on the basis

of which speech work with schoolchildren is carried out, and d) the cognitive and communicative tasks set by the teacher.

PRESENTATION is a written retelling of a text read or listened to and analyzed. AN ESSAY is the writer's own reflections on a literary work or an excerpt from it that has been read and analyzed in various written speech genres. In a presentation, the writer reproduces the finished text of a work or an excerpt from it; in an essay, his own text is created. First of all, essays are divided by methodologists into two main groups: essays on literary topics (essays related to the literature course) and essays based on personal impressions, life observations, and the students' experience.

Conclusion. English is one of the richest languages in the world. Using its richness, a student of English can choose the exact and necessary words to write to convey a thought. Written speech is the ability to write correctly in a particular language, the ability to express your thoughts on paper, simply, accessibly and logically.

The methodology of teaching literature puts forward the following areas as the main areas of work on the development of schoolchildren's speech, subject to the implementation of the approach's activities:

1. Vocabulary and phraseological work with the text of a work of fiction and literary-critical materials.
2. Teaching schoolchildren various types and genres of monologues on literary topics from retellings of the text to individual creative statements.
3. Organization of speech activity of schoolchildren in the process of dialogic communication.
4. Creation of speech situations that stimulate the development of schoolchildren's speech on an activity basis.
5. Activation of interdisciplinary interactions in literature lessons in the aspect of speech activity.

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